

FLIPPED CLASSROOM: ENGAGING STUDENTS IN PRE-CLASS PREPARATION

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Abstract

This paper presents work done in designing the pre-class component of flipped classroom for a Year 3 core module entitled *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* in the Diploma in Chemical Engineering. The pre-class activities include watching video-based lectures and other activities such as reading a journal or visit to places of interest. This paper focuses on the creation of audio-narrated slideshows outside of teaching spaces for online dissemination, using a set of core principles of learning coupled with the creative use of EduTech (Web 2.0) tools to design an interesting online learning environment that motivates students to come to class better prepared. This paper first presents a concise summary of effectiveness of online learning compared to more 'traditional' face-to-face teaching; followed by a discussion on the challenges of designing in implementing flipped classroom, in terms of student motivation to complete the pre-class activities. The paper shares a template based on these core principles of learning that can be used to plan and design a flipped classroom, in a series of learning progressions, with probing questions to guide the lecturer in the process. The template also prompts the user to think about how the choice of EduTech tools to use, to support student learning. Also shared is a typical webpage layout that serves to illustrate how the core principles of learning and the EduTech tools are creatively used to support the desired learning. Briefly, this involves first and foremost breaking the materials to be learnt into manageable segments or 'chunks', sequence them in meaningful order so that the learning outcomes are clear, and allow students to continually build new knowledge based on prior learning. In this manner, good thinking is promoted, which help in understanding the inter-relationship between different topics. The learning tasks are supported by motivational strategies, opportunities for deliberate practice in non-threatening environment with timely feedback using self-evaluation questions. Finally, the paper presents results of a survey on students' experience in using the web site in terms of its usefulness, content organization and effectiveness in helping them prepare for flipped classroom; and concludes with some ideas to move forward.

Keywords: *Chemical Engineering, Flipped Classroom, Online Engagement, EduTech tools*

Introduction

Flipped classroom has been implemented for the core module *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention* in the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) since April 2015. The pedagogy for designing flipped classroom and the design of in-class activities had been presented by Cheah (2016). This paper is a follow-up of that work, focusing on the design of pre-class component of flipped classroom. By this the author refers to activities that the lecturer wants students to engage in before coming to class. The activities include watching video-based lectures or other activities such as reading a journal or visit to places of interest. Video-based lectures can be video recording of live lectures (i.e. lecture capture) or lectures produced using web-based lecture technologies, i.e. created from computers outside of teaching spaces and rendered in various formats such as podcasts and audio-narrated slideshows for online dissemination. This paper focuses on the latter, using a set of core principles of learning coupled with the creative of EduTech tools in the design on an online learning environment that motivates students to come to class better prepared.

Brief Review of Effectiveness of Online Learning

The effectiveness of online learning versus traditional (face-to-face) lecture continues to be a hotly contested one (Cardall, et al, 2008; Dziuban & Moskal, 2011). In 2010, the U.S. Department of Education published a comprehensive study that compared online learning with the traditional format. The study, which analyzed 45 studies and measured quantitatively student learning outcomes and calculated the effect size; conclude that on average, students in an online format performed modestly better than those in the traditional format (Means, et al, 2010). However, the findings were challenged by others, e.g. Jaggars & Bailey (2010) who pointed out some omissions from the study. There are also reports that questioned the differences in student rating of online courses and traditional on-campus courses, as students can be influenced by variables other than teaching effectiveness. For example, Rovai, et al (2009) reported that online students tended to rate online course more extremely and more negatively than they did equivalent on-campus courses, and concluded

that there exist biases in student perceptions and hence their rating. Lack (2013) carried out another meta-analysis of recent publications and concluded that these studies did not provide enough evidence for assessing whether online learning is significantly more or less effective than the traditional face-to-face format. A more recent study by Nyugen (2015) classifies the findings into 3 categories: positive, negative, and mixed and null. The author reported that the number of studies that found mixed or negative significant effects for student learning outcomes in the online format is smaller by a full order of magnitude compared to positive or no significant effects. The author hence conclude that online learning is generally at least as effective as the traditional format.

The above findings have important bearing on the design of flipped classroom, which tend to depend heavily on pre-packaged video recordings of lesson materials that students must watch before coming to class. One may be tempted to cite the above “stalemate” as reservations of adopting flipped classroom. The author would challenge this position, citing the following from Lack (2013):

“It is important to remember that the lack to date of compelling quantitative evidence of learning effectiveness does not imply that the rapidly increasing number of efforts to employ online learning is a mistake – not at all. The consistency of findings in even imperfect studies of learning outcomes mistake ...suggests that determined efforts should be made to improve online learning, taking full advantage of features that are specific to an online environment, such as automatic and interactive feedback loops.”

Challenge of Flipped Classroom: Pre-Class Lessons

It is clear from the literature that flipped classroom, just like other form of active learning, requires engaged students (Pienta, 2016). However, not all students are motivated to put in the required effort to learn pre-class lesson materials on their own before coming to class. Motivation and engagement are important drivers of deep learning (Kuh, 2003). But these students lack “homework culture” (Straw, et al, 2015) and may come to class unprepared to participate in class activities.

Engagement is an important factor impacting learning: if students perceived that a learning experience was of value to their learning, they were more likely to use it (von Kinsky, et al, 2009). Murray, et al (2012) suggested that students selectively access course content based upon the degree to which they perceive it will positively influence performance and outcomes on assignments and assessments. Due to time constraints, students tend to employ strategies that they perceive will provide an optimal outcome (Murray et al, 2013). The challenge for educators, especially those embarking on flipped classroom, is to design interesting pre-class online learning materials that students want to read up. Some authors recommended giving marks to students for completing their requisite pre-class readings, but this is not a position advocated by this author. Instead, he seeks to motivate students by designing engaging pre-

class learning tasks that are closely coupled to what they will actually be doing in class. The design approach of these tasks is solidly grounded in core principles of learning, delivered via web-based platform mediated by creative use of EduTech (Web 2.0) tools.

Designing Online Lessons using the Core Principles of Learning

Sale’s 10 Core Principles of Learning (Sale, 2015), as shown below, are based on his extensive review of the literature on human learning and studies on effective teaching professionals in a range of educational contexts.

1. Motivational strategies are incorporated into the design of learning experiences
2. Learning goals, objectives and proficiency expectations are clearly visible to learners
3. Learners prior knowledge is activated and connected to new learning
4. Content is organized around key concepts and principles that are fundamental to understanding the structure of a subject
5. Good thinking promotes the building of understanding
6. Instructional methods and presentation mediums engage the range of human of senses
7. Learning design takes into account the working of memory systems
8. The development of expertise requires deliberate practice
9. A psychological climate is created which is both success-orientated and fun
10. Assessment practices are integrated into the learning design to promote desired learning outcomes and provide quality feedback

Description of Work Done

The core principles of learning are applied to the design of online lessons for the module *Plant Safety & Loss Prevention* are described in the following paragraphs for the remainder of this section. A template that is used for the design of learning tasks is shown in Figure 1. A website for the pre-class activities has been created using a template as shown in Figure 2. Figures 3-8 show selected sample web pages.

As shown in Figure 1, the contents are carefully sequenced so that the topics are centred around the concepts of chemical process plant lifecycle, and principles of loss prevention (Principle No.4). For every lesson, the topics are organized using the “learning progression” approach (Popham, 2011) in which the key topics are carefully sequenced to achieve a certain desired learning outcome (knowledge and/or skill). Online lectures are therefore created in bite sizes, or “chunks” (Miller, 1956), to make it manageable for students to digest key points, hence avoid over-taxing the working memory (Principle No.7). This approach also allows the students to gradually build up their understanding of the topics, by making connections between current mini-lecture with those that learnt in

earlier mini-lectures (Principle No.3). All learning outcomes are communicated to students (Principle No.2). For example, as can be seen in Figure 2, the lesson starts with clear explanation of the learning objectives, followed by a series of short, mini-lectures of 3-6 minutes duration. After the general concept of LOPA is presented, the concept of SIS is then introduced. To help students better understand SIS, a comparison with another topic (the BPCS) that they learnt before in another module is used (Principle No.5). To get students to watch the pre-class mini-lectures, several motivational strategies are used (Principle No.1). At the end of each mini-lecture, a short video clip offering additional assistance to students who needed help in mastering the topic presented (Figures 3 and 4) is made available, thereby providing opportunity for them to practice in a non-threatening environment (Principle No.9). They can also attempt to apply what they learnt in the lecture to real-world scenario such as that in Figure 5 (Principle No.8). Students are also encouraged to complete the pre-class preparation by being informed of the activities that will take place in class (Figure 6). All these are created using various EduTech tools as appropriate), thereby engaging students in a range of human senses (Principle No.6).

Figure 1. Template for Flipped Classroom Design

Lastly, at the end of the lesson, students can also practice what they learn in a series of true/false and multiple-choice questions as shown in Figure 7. Brief explanations are given when students selected the wrong answers (Principle No.10). Lastly, opportunity is also given for students to inform the lecturer topics which they still do not understand (Figure 8) who will promptly address them online.

Students Experience in using the Online Resources

We carried out a survey using a 5-point Likert Scale, ranging from "1" (Strongly Disagree) to "5" (Strongly

Agree), to ascertain the usefulness and effectiveness of the web site and learning resources in helping them prepare for flipped classroom.

In this week, we will start a new Chapter: 2 Plant Safety Systems. Go through the mini-lectures below for what is in store:

CP5033 Plant Safety & Loss Prevention

Chapter 2: Plant Safety Systems

Learning Objectives

Click on the image for a mini-lecture on this topic

First, let's understand the concept of Layer of Protection Analysis

CP5033 Plant Safety & Loss Prevention

Chapter 2: Plant Safety Systems

Layer of Protection Analysis (LOPA)

Click on the image for a mini-lecture on this topic

Are you able to draw a LOPA Diagram now? If you needed help, check out this [LINK](#).

Now, let's take a look at a key component of LOPA: Safety Instrumented System (SIS)

CP5033 Plant Safety & Loss Prevention

Chapter 2: Plant Safety Systems

Safety Instrumented System (SIS)

Click on the image for a mini-lecture on this topic

Now, if you need help in drawing an SIS representation in a PFD, [click HERE](#).

TEST YOURSELF: Watch [this YouTube video](#) from U.S. Chemical Safety Board, and identify LOPA elements that, if implemented, could have prevented the incident. [HINT: BPCS is not the answer]

Lastly, here is a discussion on similarities and differences between BPCS and SIS

CP5033 Plant Safety & Loss Prevention

Chapter 2: Plant Safety Systems

BPCS vs. SIS

Click on the image for a mini-lecture on this topic

Figure 2. Web page for Week 3 Pre-Class Activities

End of Mini Lectures, and to Prepare for Class

Chapter 2: Plant Safety Systems

See Figure 6

Click on the image for a mini-lecture on this topic

End-of-Chapter Self-Evaluation (to be completed before class)
TEST YOURSELF: How much did you understand LOPA. [CLICK HERE](#) to go to Socrative. The Room Number is the module code. The new session will be made available on FRIDAY 5.30 pm before the week's lesson in class; and the previous session will be closed before that.

Want to have a head start for one of many class activities? [CLICK HERE](#) and on the PDF on the right

See Figure 7

ANY QUESTIONS on the above topics? [CLICK HERE](#)

See Figure 8

Please use the [LINK](#) to go to Padlet and let me know. (Ideally, you do this before class, so that I can clarify in class)

Figure 2. (cont'd)

Figure 3. YouTube video showing how to draw LOPA diagram created using PowerPoint

Figure 4. YouTube video showing how to draw SIS created using VideoScribe

Students Experience in using the Online Resources

We carried out a survey using a 5-point Likert Scale, ranging from “1” (Strongly Disagree) to “5” (Strongly Agree), to ascertain the usefulness and effectiveness of the web site and learning resources in helping them prepare for flipped classroom. A total of 33 students responded to the survey, and the results are shown in Figures 9-13. In the survey, students are asked the following questions:

- Q1. The pre-class online lesson stimulated and engaged my interest in this topic.
- Q2. The pre-class online lesson provided a clear understanding of what I needed to learn and the purpose of learning the topic.
- Q3. The pre-class online lesson (e.g. videos, reading materials, quizzes) was well organized, sequenced and prepared me for the in-class activities.
- Q4. I am able to prepare myself before the lessons in Flipped Classroom, by going through the videos and other prescribed readings.
- Q5. I am able to connect the in-class activities to the pre-class online learning.
- Q6. I find the flipped classroom format of learning is better than traditional lecture style of teaching.

Figure 5. CSB Video on YouTube used for student practice of LOPA concept learnt

Figure 6. YouTube video on In-Class Activity created using Powtoon

Figure 7. Student Self-Evaluation of Learning created using Socrative

It can be said that the effort is moderately successful with mixed results. As can be seen from Figures 10, 11 and 13, students generally find the resources useful.

Despite these benefits, a significant number (42.42% Neutral and 12.12% Disagree, in Figure 9) remain unenthusiastic about learning the materials online. This may explain why an equally significant number (30.30% Neutral and 12.12% Disagree, in Figure 12) who reported having difficulty preparing for class. Perhaps such outcome is hardly surprising when one noted that more than half the respondents expressed no preferences or dislike for flipped classroom (37.50% Neutral, 18.75% Disagree, in Figure 14).

Figure 8. Feedback using Padlet

Discussions

The findings may appear somewhat perplexing at first, since some responses are clearly contradictory to one another – students reportedly understand the purpose of learning a given topic, found the materials useful, well organized and sequenced, and able to connect with what they will do in class; and yet are unable to prepare well for class. One reason could be that this is the students’ first exposure to the flipped classroom approach. The author had previously reported in an earlier work that on average, it took some students 7-8 weeks (20% of the respondents) to get used for the new learning format, and another 20% needed more than 8 weeks (Cheah, et al, 2016). At the time this survey was administered, the students had just completed 6 weeks of lessons. Hence it might be argued that many of them are still adjusting to this new method of learning and still show preference to the traditional didactic method of learning. Therefore, the design of the learning tasks can be considered to have met its intended objectives. The author will continue to monitor students’ engagement with the pre-class materials, and from time to time, highlight the benefits of flipped classroom, in order to effect a mindset change in them. And since most of our students aspire to further their education, the author will also inform them of greater adoption of flipped classroom in the universities, and as such, it is very likely that they will encounter more of such learning format in their post-diploma education.

Notwithstanding the above, another area of improvement can be to provide more varieties to the pre-class preparation work. Current design did have some non-video components, such as visit to a laboratory, and reading a technical journal. Future revamp can introduce more such components. However,

these need to be weighed against the time and resources needed.

Figure 9. Student responses to Q1.

Figure 10. Student responses to Q2.

Figure 11. Student responses to Q3.

Figure 12. Student responses to Q4.

Figure 13. Student responses to Q5.

Figure 14. Student responses to Q6.

Conclusions

This paper shares the work done in designing pre-class activities to motivate students to better prepare for flipped classroom. The findings are somewhat mixed, indicating the present cohort of students' preference for more traditional lecture style of teaching compared to flipped classroom. The students' mindset can be changed with consistent messaging of the importance of learning under a new format of flipped classroom.

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